

The Maryland-95 study

Title: Comparing Detection Methods for Software Requirements Inspections

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Definition: Evaluation of fault detection methods Ad Hoc, Checklist, and Scenario for software requirements inspections using replicated controlled experiments.

Context: Academic setting with graduate students as reviewers.

Hypothesis: Scenario-based method yields higher fault detection rates than Ad Hoc or Checklist methods.

Variables: Independent variables: Detection method, Replication, Inspection round, Specification order.

Dependent variables: Individual fault detection rate, Team fault detection rate, Meeting gain/loss rate.

Sample: 48 graduate CS students, organized into sixteen 3-person teams.

Experiment Design: 3×2 partial factorial randomized design with two replications.

Instrumentation: Software Requirements Specifications (WLMS, CRUISE), fault taxonomy, checklists, scenario procedures, fault report forms.

Validity Evaluation: Internal threats: Selection, Maturation, Replication, Instrumentation, Presentation.

External threats: Subject representativeness, Specification representativeness, Process differences.

Preparation: Two 75-minute training lectures covering SRS, SCR notation, and inspection procedures; training with ELEVATOR SRS.

Execution: Two experimental rounds per specification, including a 2-hour detection session and a 2-hour collection meeting.

Data Validation: Fault keys, reviewer responsibility mapping, and fault detection summaries at both team and individual levels.

Coverage: University of Maryland, USA.

Descriptive Statistics: Average fault detection rate, meeting gain/loss rate, standard deviation.

Dataset Reduction: Team performance analysis and individual performance analysis.

Hypothesis Testing: ANOVA for team performance; Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney tests for individual performance; null hypothesis rejection for detection method (H1, H2 evaluation).

Report: IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering, 21(6), 563–575, 1995.

Package: Laboratory kit, experimental materials, and data analysis resources.

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PORTER, A. A.; VOTTA, L. G.; BASILI, V. R. Comparing detection methods for software requirements inspections: a replicated experiment. IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering, v. 21, n. 6, p. 563–575, jun. 1995. DOI: 10.1109/32.391380. Disponível no arquivo enviado